

Self-Esteem And Social Anxiety Among Face Acne Patients In Peshawar

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 07, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: March 11, 2023</p> <p>Keywords : Self-esteem, Social Anxiety, Face Acne, Adults, Adolescents</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7719384</p>	<p><i>Acne is the most common and most prevalent disease in the world, which affect 3 in every 4 people all over the world, and which has a strong relationship with psychological issues.</i></p> <p><i>Objective of the present study was to measure level of social anxiety, and self-esteem. It was supposed that adolescent having face acne will score low on self-esteem scale, as compare to adults, another was adolescents having face acne will score higher on social anxiety scale as compared to adults. It was also hypothesized that "Those Face acne patients who score high on social anxiety scale will score low on self-esteem scale.</i></p> <p><i>Sample of the present study consist of (N=200) diagnosed patients, which were divided in to two groups' male adolescents, and adults (n=100), and female adolescents, and adults (n=100). Scales of the study were liebowitz social anxiety scale, (LSAS), Rosenberg self-esteem scale (RSES). T-Test (independent sample t-test), and Pearson's correlation was used for analysis of data.</i></p> <p><i>Present study concludes that there was high level of social anxiety, and low level of self-esteem among adolescents as compared to adults.</i></p>

Introduction

A beautiful face is a desire and dream of every human being especially during adolescence, where whole life is going around the beautiful appearance and its center region is face, for this purpose they madly used every Cleanser, Toner, Moisturizer, face wash, sunblock, in fact, every latest beauty product of the local market, they are unaware about the skincare product that best match their skin, they have no knowledge that these products are like poison for the skin which destroy the dermal layer of their face. Because of no knowledge, they are unaware of the universal fact that adolescence is a period of puberty that has a common sign in the form of facial acne (Cobb, 2017).

Acne is a skin disease that mainly occurs on the dermal layer of the skin called hair follicle (small holes in the skin), which are blocked by dirt that prevents the dead skin and oil from the skin. According to the world health organization, (1997) Acne mostly occur on the part of the skin that has excessive oil glands and these glands are called sebaceous gland basically hair follicles are connected with these oil glands (Elsaie, 2016). It negatively affects 3 individuals in every 4 people aged around 11 to 30 years (Cobb, 2017). There are two major types of acne inflammatory and non-inflammatory. Its intensity is characterized by three levels, mild (pimples, blackheads, & whiteheads) moderate (papules & pustules), and the more severe form (nodules & cysts) (Suva et al., 2015).

Self-esteem is a combination of two words self and esteem. According to the oxford dictionary of the English language, (1989) self means one's own personal nature that is different from others and esteem means the condition of being valued. Self-worth or the positive feelings about one's own self is called self-esteem (Rosenberg, 1965). Self-esteem is individual positive feelings towards one's own self such as self-love, admiration, belief about his own skills, confidence about his own talent, decision-making, and everyday functioning (Sedikides & Gress, 2003). Self-esteem is known as a universal psychological personality trait. Adolescence and early adulthood is the period of one's life for the development of self-esteem (Jung, 1971). It is common in adolescence to compare yourself with others. Normally they compare their complexion and face but when they have a face full of acne, they feel unattractive and start to feel bad, less valued, and less worthy of themselves. When acne occurs it affects self-esteem which causes difficulty at work and in social situations (Kimball, 2013). The relationship between appearance and self-esteem is important, a beautiful look can sky-high our self-esteem, and being ugly can lead to kill self-esteem as a result, the person was too afraid to spend time with friends and in other social circles, which means it greatly affects relationships with others (Pickhardt, 2010). Lack of self-esteem leads adolescents far away from the outer world and leads to social anxiety disorder.

Social anxiety disorder is fear of being in front of others, typically avoiding having eye contact, eating, speaking, and performing in front of others and, thinking that everyone negatively thinking about him (Richards, 2014). The age of onset is teenage or mid-adolescence (Schneiet al., 1992). The same is the age of occurring face acne as a common sign of puberty (Magdy, Darwish, & Al-rubaya, 2013). When they go out of their home they think all the time that people were staring at and negatively thinking about them because they

are looking ugly and unattractive. This inaccurate and irrational fear strongly affect their lives, as a result, the adolescent fails to maintain relation with friends and other social circles.

A study on “The impact of acne and facial post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation on quality of life and self-esteem of newly admitted Nigerian undergraduates” was conducted by Akinboro, (2018). Aim of the study was to measure the quality of life, self-esteem, and psychosocial variables. 200 subjects with age range was 23-34 years were included. Scales of the study include the Rosenberg self-esteem scale, Cardiff acne disability index, acne severity measured by US food and drug administration. Results of the study showed an association between acne and low self-esteem and poor quality of life.

Schroeder, Kaplan, & Feldman, (2012) examine the psychological impact of acne on self-esteem among adolescents. Researchers focus on how acne effect self-esteem, for this purpose they used previous 5 research papers to find the complete reviews of the data. Researchers stated that with the severity of acne self-esteem decreased, and with the successful treatment of acne self-esteem increased. Result based on the careful analysis of these 5 research papers, indicate that acne patient’s perception of the severity of acne leads to decreased self-esteem, and successful treatment can increased self-esteem and lower the risk of suicidal ideation, and depression.

A study on “Acne in adolescents: quality of life, self-esteem, mood, and psychological disorders” was conducted by Dunn et al. (2011). Result of these 16 selected studies confirmed that acne leads to lower quality of life, and self-esteem. Psychological disorders are more prevalent in acne sufferers as compared to normal people, and psychological problems should also be considered in the process of treatment.

Hafez et al. (2009) conducted a study on “The impact of acne vulgaris on the quality of life and psychological status in patients from upper Egypt”. Sample of the present study was “50 controls”, and 150 acne patients”. The study examines the effect of acne on the quality of life and psychological functioning of acne sufferers in Egypt. The scales of the study were Dermatology Life Quality Index, Symptom Check List-90 – Revised, and Culture Free Self-Esteem Inventory – Adult Version. Result of the study highlights a significant negative impact on psychological functioning, quality of life, and showed a negative association between acne and self-esteem in acne sufferers as compared to the control group.

“Anxiety, depression, social phobia, and quality of life, in Turkish patients with acne and their relationships with the severity of acne” was measured by Ozturket al. (2013). The study aimed to find out psychological characteristics and quality of life among acne sufferers. 120 patients were include in the study, each one is 16-30 years old. Result indices that with the severity of acne level of social anxiety, depression, anxiety increase, and quality of life decreased.

Unal, Emiroğlu, & Cengiz, (2016) conducted a study on “Evaluation of social anxiety, self-esteem, life quality in adolescents with acne vulgaris”. Objective of the study was to assess level of social anxiety, self-esteem, and acne related quality of life, among acne sufferers. 102 acne sufferers and 83 control group, ages between 12-17 years was participated in the study. Result of the study revealed high social anxiety level, impaired quality of life, and low self-esteem in adolescents’ acne patients.

“Prevalence of mental health problems in acne patients” was find out by Khan, Naeem, & Mufti, (2001). For this purpose they take 50 acne and 50 seborrhea skin patients, age 12 to 25. Result of this study indicates 38% acne sufferers were suffering from depression as compared to seborrhea patient, prevalence of social anxiety was more in acne patients (34%) as compared to seborrhea (10%).

Acne is skin disease. It effects 3 in every 4 people aged between “11- 30”. As it’s a skin disease which has direct connection with beauty and attractiveness (Davern, & O’Donnell, 2018). Keeping in view the population range and its connection with psychological factors among acne sufferers, all over the world researchers conduct studies on overall acne and its psychological and psychosocial effects, but in Pakistan especially in KPK work on “face acne” is rare. So the current study aim is to examine self-esteem, and social anxiety among adolescents and adults suffering from face acne.

Objectives

- To investigate level of social anxiety among face acne patients.
- To measure level of self-esteem among face acne patients.

Hypotheses

- Adolescents having face acne will score low on the self-esteem scale as compared to adults with face acne.
- Adolescents having face acne will score high on social anxiety scale as compared to adults with face acne.
- Those Face acne patients will score high on social anxiety scale will score low on self-esteem scale.

Methodology

Sample

The sample of the present study will consist of 200(N = 200) face acne patients with equal number of male and female adolescents (n =100). Age range varies from 13 to 30years. Education level will be minimum matric or those who can read the questionnaire. Patients with face acne will be randomly selected from different hospitals of Peshawar.

Instruments

Demographic sheet

Include name, gender, education, age, address, contact number.

Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale (1965)

The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale is a worldwide using scale for measuring self-esteem, developed (1965) by Rosenberg. It is 10 item, 4-point likert scale. Scores between 15 &25 suggest normal self-esteem and scores below15 indicates low self-esteem. Reliability range for the scale is from 0.82 to 0.85 (Rosen berg, 1965).

Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (1987)

To investigate social anxiety disorder, a researcher and psychiatrist at university of Columbia "Michael liebowitz" developed (1987) the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale. The scale consist of 24 questionnaires, which is divided into two sub parts. The first part is related to performance anxiety and the other is related to social situation. These 24 questionnaires are answered on a likert scale from 0 to 3. The scales divided in to two parts fear of social situation and avoidance of the situation. Reliability for the scores on fear and social interaction with correlation were .95 & .96 (Dossantoset al., 2013).

Procedure

Formal permission will be taken for data collection, from the hospitals (LRH, KTH, CMH, RMI, and North West hospital) of Peshawar city. After approval participants will briefed about the objective of the study. Before collecting data, consent form will be given to the participants and ensured them about the confidentiality of the data, that it will be used only for research purpose. First demographics will be given to them, after that two scales will administered on them, that is Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale.

Result

The objective of the present study was to find out self-esteem, and social anxiety among male and female adolescents. The study population included (N=200) participants, which consist of (n=100) male adolescents, and (n=100) female adolescents.

Appropriate statistical test were run for analysis of the data, and all the procedure was carried out by using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 20.

Table-1

Psychometric properties of the scales

Scales items	M	SD	Range		a	
			potential	actual		
RSES	10	38.55	25.4	0-40	0-27	.887
LSAS	24	90.72	21.5	0-30	0-94	.987

The reliability analysis of the scales indicated that both the scales has high internal consistency and is best scales for the collection of data.

Table-2

Mean score, Slander deviation and t value of scores of adolescence and adult on Rosenberg self-esteem scale.

(95%CI)							
Group	M	SD	t	p	LL	UL	Cohen's d
(Adolescence)	17.5	4.3	-17.398	.000	-12.0	-9.58	2.4
(Adult)	28.3	4.4			-12.0	-9.58	

Note; CI stand for class interval, LL stand for lower limit, UL stand for upper limit.

Result showed that adolescence scores significantly (P<.000) low on self-esteem scale as compare to adults. The result support the first hypothesis of the study which states that "Adolescents having face acne will score low on the self-esteem as compared to adults with face acne".

Table-3

Mean score, standard deviation and t value of scores of adolescence and adult on liebowitz social anxiety scale.

(95% CI)							
Group	M	SD	t	P	LL	UL	Cohen's d
(Adolescence)	61.0	9.28	26.87	.000	41.71	48.32	3.7
(Adult)							

(Adult)	16.0	14.4	41.73	48.64
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Table-3 presents mean difference between adult and adolescence on liebowitz social anxiety scale. Result in the table shows significantly ($P < .000$) high social anxiety in adolescence as compare to adults. Result support the second hypothesis which is “Adolescents having face acne will score higher on the social anxiety scale as compared to adults with face acne”.

Table-4

Pearson's correlation of face acne patients on social anxiety scale and self-esteem scale (N= 200).

Variables	
1. High Social anxiety	
	-.809**
2. Low self-esteem	

Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Table-4 shows that there is significantly strong negative correlation between social anxiety and self-esteem of face acne patients, it means when social anxiety increase self-esteem decrease, which support hypothesis of the study, which stated that “Face acne patients will score high on social anxiety scale will score low on self-esteem scale”.

Discussion

Acne is a skin disease which commonly occur on face which is common in adolescence (Revol, Milliez, Gerard, 2015). According to Dalgard et al. (2008) its occurrence leads to psychological issues. The current study aim was to find out difference between adult and adolescence’s level of self-esteem, and social anxiety.

Self-esteem is psychological personality trait. Adolescence and early adulthood is the period of one’s life for the development of self-esteem (Jung, 1971). It is common in adolescence to compare themselves with others. Normally they compare their beauty and face but when they have acne on their face, they feel ugly and start to feel bad, less valued and less worthy about their self. The relationship between appearance and self-esteem is important, beautiful look can sky-high our self-esteem and ugly can lead to kill self-esteem.

First hypothesis of the study is “Adolescents having face acne will score low on the self-esteem scale as compared to adults with face acne”.

Result of the present study (table 3) revealed highly significant difference between the scores of adolescence and adult. The same findings is supported by Dharshana et al. (2016) Study of “Depression, mood change and self-esteem among adolescents aged 12-25 years with acne vulgaris in India”. 150 participants were included in the study which consist of 50 females with 100 controls ages between “12-25”. Result indicated low self-esteem higher level of depression, more than half 58% of participants experience anger about their skin. Vilor, Santos, & Filho, (2015) study “Quality of life, self-esteem, and psychosocial factors in adolescents with acne vulgaris”. 355 subjects were participated in the study, average age was between 16 years. The study examine the correlation between self-esteem, quality of life, and psychosocial variables among adolescents’ patients with acne and without acne population. Result showed low quality of life in acne suffers and show negative correlation between self-esteem. Khan, (2017) determine Acne and it’s associations with psychosocial well-being among adolescents in Nellore (India). Scales of the study were Beck depression inventory, and self-made standard questionnaire. Result revealed that 33% participants were emotionally effected by acne, 52% were affected by decreased self-esteem, 43% were not happy about their appearance, 41% were sad about their appearance, 31% were hopeless that one day their acne will go.

Adolescence is a time when adolescence are moving from their family interaction to their friends and other social circle (Larson and Richards 1991), same age is a period of puberty, which cause dramatic changes in appearance, behavior, emotions (Deardorff et al., 2007). Adolescence focus on their appearance specially on their face, when acne occur on their face it ruin their beauty, beautiful appearance is much more important in this century then the previous age (Revol, Milliez, Gerard, 2015). Adolescence having acne on face think that all the people around negatively looking to their face, which make them to avoid social situations. Simple conversation became unbearable for them as they think that people only looking at their face instead of listening them.

Second hypothesis of the study is “Adolescents having face acne will score high on social anxiety scale as compared to adults with face acne”.

Result on (table-4) proved our hypothesis and demonstrate highly significant difference between adolescence and adult score, which supported second hypothesis. Other researches also proved that people having acne have

high level of social anxiety. According to Sereflican et al. (2017) that people having acne has a prevalence of type D personality, and high level of depression, anxiety, social anxiety, self-reported stress, anxiety sensitivity, disability. "Impact of Social Anxiety on patients suffering from Acne Vulgaris: A Hospital Based Study in a Tertiary Care Set up" was determined by Jentilal, (2019). 90 participants were included in the sample. Result of the study indicates that patients having acne on their face has high level of social anxiety. Loney, Standage, & Lewis, (2008) findings are also consistent with the present study which measures Psychological effects of dermatological-related social anxiety in a sample of acne patients. 50 participants were included in the sample. Aim of the study was to find out general self-esteem, quality of life, dermatological related social anxiety, and to determine their intention to participate in sports/exercise. Scales of the study included Rosenberg self-esteem scale, intention to participate in sports/exercise, social physique anxiety scale, dermatology life quality index. Result revealed negative quality of life, decreased self-esteem, increased dermatological-related quality of life, and also proved that patients with acne who has dermatology related social anxiety has lower or no intention to participate in exercise/sport. Third hypothesis of the present study is "Face acne patients will score high on social anxiety scale will score low on self-esteem scale".

Research supported result of the present study "Acne relationship with psychiatric and psychological morbidity, result of school based cohort study of adolescents" was conducted by Magin et al. (2010). The hypothesis of the study is adolescents with acne effect personality traits and has psychological problems as compare to adults with acne. The result of the study concluded association between psychological factors and acne such as anxiety, depression, public self-consciousness and social anxiety and effects on personality traits such as introversion, extraversion, and neuroticism in adolescents as compare to adults. "Social anxiety level in acne vulgaris patients and its relationship to clinical variables" was investigated by Yolacet et al. (2008). Sample of the study include 83 acne sufferers and 58 healthy controls. Result showed that the level of social anxiety, depression, and negative automatic thoughts were increased, and self-esteem was decreased in acne sufferers as compared to the control group. Bez et al. (2011) measured "High social phobia frequency and related disability in patients with acne vulgaris". Aim of the study was to measure level of social anxiety, depression, and acne related disability. For this purpose researchers used global acne system, liebowitz social anxiety scale, hospital anxiety and depression scale, and shaheen disability scale. 178 acne patients, ranging between 15 to 33 years, were include in the study. Result of the study indicates higher social anxiety, increased depression, higher performance avoidance and higher disability scores in their daily life. A Study was conducted by Salman et al. (2016) to investigate Social Anxiety and Quality of Life in Vitiligo and Acne Patients with Facial Involvement. Aim of the study was to find out level of social anxiety, quality of life, depression, anxiety in patients with facial acne and vitiligo. 37 acne and 37 vitiligo, with 18 years of age were include in the study. Liebowitz social anxiety scale, hospital anxiety and depression scale, and dermatology life quality index were administered. Result of the study revealed higher level of social anxiety, anxiety, increased depression, negative quality of life in face acne patients, result also showed positive correlation between anxiety, poor quality of life, depression, social anxiety in vitiligo patients. Gallitano, & Berson, (2018) conducted a study on "How Acne Bumps Cause the Blues: The Influence of Acne Vulgaris on Self-Esteem". The aim of the study was to determine previous 13 research articles data related to acne and its impact on self-esteem. Result of all these 13 studies showed that acne effect self-esteem in every period of age, and most commonly and very strongly effect female's self-esteem. Sample include all age group. All these 13 research studies are conducted in different 11 countries of the world. Different assessment styles were used in these studies although most commonly used were dermatology life quality index (DLQI), and Rosen Berg self-esteem scale (RSES). Careful review of these studies demonstrate that acne have a negative impact on self-esteem, and Female's self-esteem was more effected as compared to males. Shaikh et al. (2020) measures "impact of acne vulgaris on self-esteem in adolescents and young adult". Objective of the present study was to assess the psychological effects of acne on self-esteem in adults and adolescents. 158 diagnosed acne patients was included in the sample. Rosen berg self-esteem scale was use to evaluate self-esteem of the patients. Result of the study revealed that acne negatively affect self-esteem, and self-esteem was low in females as compared to male.

Conclusion

Acne is skin condition, which is more prevalent among adolescence and early adults, every year it effects 85% people all around the world. Skin is body organ which is visible specially face, so it has more psychological effects than any other disease, which is hidden. It mostly effects young adolescents, when they are undergoing physical, emotional, psychological, and social changes, according to Fried, Weschler, (2006) 30%-50% adolescents have psychological issues related to their acne. The present study measure social anxiety, and self-esteem among adolescents and adults.

What adolescents think about themselves is the result of what they are listing about their look and appearance from others. When acne occur, and someone ask about it they feel embarrassed and create negative thoughts about their appearance. So physical appearance is one of the main factor that effect self-esteem. Adolescents is

the time when they develop social anxiety, and it is the same time when acne occur as a sign of puberty. So when adolescents goes out of their home they think that all the people looking at their acne they feel embarrassed for their acne. Result shows that adolescents having face acne have higher social anxiety, and lower self-esteem as compare to adults, is because adolescents more focus on their beauty, and adult more focus on their, family issues, career and on their future rather than beauty.

Limitations

In the field of social sciences every researcher try his best to make study limitation free but it can hardly be in any case. Current study has the following limitations.

- The first limitation of the study is that it focus on age and gender, whereas work on other demographic variables such as education (only educated people were studied and uneducated people were ignored), marital status, living style (urban, and rural areas) socio demographic status which has also impact on human minds were ignored.
- The research data was collected only from Peshawar, data sample from Peshawar was not the representative of all the face acne patients.
- Sample size should be increased, the current sample size is (N=200), for better result sample size should be increased. Current study sample age is from “13-30”, future studies needed bigger sample size with all age groups, so small sample size is another limitation of the study.
- Present study not measure intensity level of acne, with the severity of acne, psychological issues become more increase, so future studies need to work on the intensity level.
- Acne is skin issue, and skin is the body organ, which is always on the display, it means issues on the skin has more psychological issues other than studied in the current study, so more work is needed in future to find out other psychological issues related with acne.
- It was hospital based study, which consist of only diagnosed patients, other than diagnosed patients face acne sufferers still exists in general population, and students who may not visit doctors for some reason, these individual also be considered for future studies.
- Present study measure psychological effects of facial acne, whereas acne on other parts of the body has also psychological effect, is also become the limitation of the study.

Suggestions

Following are the suggestions for future studies:

- Use large sample size in research paper, the more the sample size increased the more the result will be more generalize.
- Research data should be expend from Peshawar to other areas.
- Before and after treatment psychological effects should also be considered in future studies.
- Acne on different parts of the body, hormonal acne, and PCOS related acne which is appear on the face along with facial hairs in female adolescents. Hormonal acne is also prevalent and more severe in the early adolescents which has serious psychological effect on the minds of adolescents, hormonal acne will also need to study for finding out psychological issues.
- In future before and after treatment related variables should also be considered. Treatment of acne leads to lower or decreased psychological effects, so work on treatment related decreased psychological symptoms also need to study in future.

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